

Tasks

The following code comprehension tasks were given:

- Minimum [RT-ForEach]: Describe the purpose of this code. In other words, if the code would be placed in a function, give an appropriate name for the function.

```
class Main {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        int[] rainValues = {25, 70, 70, 70, 76, 76, 0, 34};
        int current = rainValues[0];
        for (int value : rainValues) {
            if (value < current) {
                current = value;
            }
        }
        System.out.println(current);
    }
}
```

- Maximum [RT-While]: Describe the purpose of this code. In other words, if the code would be placed in a function, give an appropriate name for the function.

```
class Main {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        int[] rainValues = {25, 70, 70, 70, 76, 76, 0, 34};
        int current = rainValues[0];
        int i = 0;
        while (i < rainValues.length) {
            if (rainValues[i] > current) {
                current = value[i];
            }
            i++;
        }
        System.out.println(current);
    }
}
```

- Count [RT-For]: Describe the purpose of this code. In other words, if the code would be placed in a function, give an appropriate name for the function.

```
class Main {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        int[] rainValues = {25, 70, 70, 70, 76, 76, 0, 34};
        int count = 0;
        for (int i = 0; i < rainValues.length; i++) {
            if (rainValues[i] == 0) {
                count++;
            }
        }
        System.out.println(count);
    }
}
```

The following code composition tasks were given:

- **Frequency of maximum** [WT-MaxFreq]: A weather station kept track of rainfall for a number of days. Here is an example:

```
rainValues = {25, 70, 70, 70, 76, 76, 0, 34};
```

In this example you can see that it rained 76 mm on the wettest day. This happened on 2 days. Write a program that prints on how many days the maximum amount of rain fell.

- **First and last rainy day** [*WT-FirstLast*]: A weather station kept track of rainfall for a number of days. Here is an example:

```
rainValues = {25, 70, 70, 70, 76, 76, 0, 34};
```

Write a program that prints the index of the first rainy day and the index of the last rainy day. If there are no rainy days, print an error message. The output for this example would be:

```
index of first rainy day: 0, index of last rainy day: 7
```

- **Bar chart** [*WT-BarChart*]: A weather station kept track of rainfall for a number of days. Here is an example:

```
rainValues = {3,4,0,1,2};
```

Plot these values in a horizontal bar chart. Each row should show the daily rainfall using asterisks: one asterisk for each mm of rain. In this example the following would be printed:

```
***
****
*
**
```

- **Merging lists** [*WT-Merge*]: A weather station keeps track of daily rainfall using two instruments. Each instrument measures the rainfall every other day. Here is an example:

```
rainValues1 = {25, 30, 70, 50};
rainValues2 = {34, 72, 76, 0};
```

The weather station then merges both lists, by taking an element from each list alternating:

the first element from *rainValues1*, then the first from *rainValues2*, then the second from the *rainValues1*, etc.. This is the result:

```
rainValuesMerged = {25, 34, 30, 72, 70, 76, 50, 0};
```

Write a program that, given two lists, prints a merged list (values are chosen by alternating from each list). You may assume both lists are of the same length.

Below is some code to get you started using either `array` or `arrayList` which you can copy and paste if you wish.

Using arrays:

```
class Main {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        int[] rainValues1 = {25, 30, 70, 50};
        int[] rainValues2 = {34, 72, 76, 0};
        int[] rainValuesMerged = new int[8];
        // TYPE YOUR CODE HERE
    }
}
```

Using arraylists:

```
import java.util.ArrayList;
import java.util.Arrays;
```

```

class Main {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        ArrayList<Integer> rainValues1
            = new ArrayList<>(Arrays.asList(25,30,70,50));
        ArrayList<Integer> rainValues2
            = new ArrayList<>(Arrays.asList(34,72,76,0));
        ArrayList<Integer> rainValuesMerged
            = new ArrayList<>();
        // TYPE YOUR CODE HERE
    }
}

```

- **Average [WT-Average]:** A weather station keeps track of daily rainfall. Sometimes a malfunctioning instrument will report a negative value. Here is an example:

```
rainValues = {25, 70, 70, 70, 76, -99, 0, 34};
```

Write a program that prints the average value of the non-negative values (0 and positive). In this example the average would be calculated as follows:

$$\text{average} = (25+70+70+70+76+0+34)/7$$

In each case the skeleton code was provided. For the first two tasks it was the following code:

```

class Main {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        int[] rainValues = {25, 70, 70, 70, 76, 76, 0, 34};

        // TYPE YOUR CODE HERE

    }
}

```